

Data-Driven Modeling for Fault Detection in a Solar Thermal Concentrator

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Abstract—Accurate predictive modeling of solar thermal systems is essential to ensure operational reliability, stable thermal performance, and reduced maintenance costs. This paper presents a data-driven predictive modeling framework, validated on a fully operational Solar Thermal Concentrator (STC) equipped with real-time IoT-based monitoring, enabling early identification of anomalous and faulty system behavior. Dynamic models, including Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (ARX), Nonlinear Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (NARX), as well as Random Forest Regression (RFR) are developed to estimate key thermal variables, namely inlet and outlet fluid temperatures, storage tank temperature, and delivered thermal power. A systematic predictor selection strategy, combining correlation analysis and exhaustive search is implemented using ARX, NARX and RFR models, leading to a set of results that depends on the evaluated predictors. The results demonstrate strong predictive performance across all the models, achieving coefficients of determination R^2 ranging from 0.89 to 0.99. These high values confirm that the system dynamics are accurately captured within the limited operating range and meteorological conditions represented by the September dataset. ARX is effective for fast, low-inertia temperature dynamics and suitable for real-time deployment, RFR excels at modeling high-inertia thermal storage, and NARX achieves the highest accuracy for variables with nonlinear thermodynamic behavior. A simulated fault scenario confirms the framework’s ability to detect abnormal conditions, demonstrating its potential for reliable, data-driven predictive maintenance under the evaluated operating conditions.

Keywords—Fault Detection, Machine Learning, Solar Thermal Concentrator, Data-driven Modeling

I. INTRODUCTION

A. Background And Motivation

Solar thermal collector technologies play a key role in the global transition toward carbon-neutral energy systems, offering high-efficiency heat generation directly from renewable solar resources [1], [2]. However, the thermal performance of these systems strongly depends on their operational stability and the proper functioning of key components. Numerous studies show that factors such as component degradation, hydraulic malfunctions, solar tracking inaccuracies, and sensor-related disturbances can significantly reduce system efficiency and hinder reliable energy delivery [3], [4]. Fault detection has long been recognized as a key requirement for ensuring reliability, efficiency, and safety of the systems. Early work in [5]

established the foundations of fault detection through model-based methods, defining a structured process from fault detection to fault tolerance based on analytical redundancy and system modeling. These approaches rely on physical models and mathematical representations to detect deviations from expected behavior, enabling systematic classification and diagnosis of system faults. However, their effectiveness is highly dependent on accurate modeling, which can become challenging in complex or variable operating environments such as renewable energy systems [6].

In the domain of solar energy, the increasing deployment of Photovoltaic (PV) and solar thermal installations has intensified research on automated fault detection to avoid energy losses and costly maintenance interventions. The review in [7] highlights the diversity of fault types in large solar thermal systems and examines existing detection techniques, ranging from physical modeling to data-driven approaches. In parallel, [8] shows that for solar panels, data-driven evaluation methods offer promising advancements due to their ability to handle nonlinear behaviors and evolving system conditions. Building on this trend, recent studies demonstrate the growing maturity of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in fault detection. The work in [9] proposes an AI-based system for automatic fault detection in solar-thermal installations, using a Random Forest Regression (RFR) model to enable robust and flexible monitoring without requiring detailed physical modeling. Meanwhile, [10] introduces a real-time machine learning framework combining digital-twin simulation with machine learning methods to enable not only fault detection but also classification and localization of faults in large-scale solar energy systems.

Machine learning techniques are increasingly used to characterize the behavior of solar energy systems directly from operational data, reducing the need for detailed physical models. Recent studies [11], [12], [13] demonstrate that data-driven approaches such as Polynomial Regression (PR) and Neural Networks (NN) can accurately model photovoltaic and hybrid Photovoltaic-Thermal (PV/T) systems by directly learning input-output relationships from measured data. Beyond static input-output modeling, dynamic data-driven models have gained growing attention for their ability to capture the temporal evolution of solar processes. Approaches based on Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (ARX), Auto Regressive Moving Average with eXogenous inputs (ARMAX), Nonlinear Auto Regressive with eXogenous inputs (NARX), and

Recurrent Neural Networks (RNN) such as Long Short Term Memory (LSTM) architectures have demonstrated strong capabilities for representing multi-scale dynamics and nonlinearities inherent to hybrid photovoltaic–thermal and solar thermal collector systems [14], [15]. These advances underline the potential of dynamic data-driven modeling to enhance fault detection and predictive maintenance by enabling early anomaly identification, improving reliability, and optimizing performance over time.

Although recent progress demonstrates the relevance of AI for performance optimization and fault diagnosis in solar energy systems, Solar Thermal Concentrator (STC) installations remain considerably under investigated, particularly under real operating conditions where measurements are affected by sensor drift, fluctuating irradiance, hydraulic variability, and environmental disturbances. Unlike PV and PV/T systems, STCs involve multi-physics energy conversion processes combining optical concentration, fluid transport, and transient heat exchange, introducing behaviors that challenge conventional diagnostic approaches. Moreover, most existing studies rely on offline analyses or synthetic datasets, and do not provide scalable solutions capable of processing live sensor streams for real-time fault detection or predictive maintenance.

To address these limitations, there is a growing need for dynamic, data-driven modeling frameworks capable of learning system behavior directly from operational data and identifying anomalies as soon as they occur. AI-based methods, combined with systematic sensor selection and robust dynamic prediction, offer a promising pathway toward intelligent monitoring. Developing such models not only enhances diagnostic reliability but also supports predictive maintenance strategies, thereby improving energy efficiency, reducing downtime, and extending the system lifespan.

B. Contribution of This Study

This paper introduces a complete data-driven framework for fault detection in an operational STC installation. A network of temperature, flow, and irradiance sensors collects process measurements and streams them to a cloud-integrated database through an IoT architecture, enabling continuous supervision of dynamic operation.

Building upon an applicable methodology, predictive models are trained to reconstruct recent advances in AI-based diagnostics, including the fault detection of the expected behavior of key thermal variables under different meteorological conditions. Faults are identified by analyzing residual deviations between predicted and actual measurements, allowing the system to infer potential causes such as component malfunctions or gradual performance drift. The main contributions of this work are as follows:

- Experimental validation of data-driven modeling for fault detection on a fully operational STC platform equipped with permanent data acquisition and supervision.
- A comparative assessment of linear dynamic (ARX), nonlinear dynamic (NARX), and static nonlinear (RFR) models for estimating key thermal outputs, including

collector inlet and outlet temperatures, storage tank temperature, and delivered thermal power.

- An interpretable anomaly-detection strategy validated through a simulated fault scenario demonstrating the effectiveness of residual-based monitoring in identifying system issues.

C. Organization of This Paper

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II describes the STC experimental installation, its thermal circuit, sensor network, and IoT-based monitoring infrastructure. Section III presents the data-driven fault detection methodology, including data preprocessing, exhaustive search conducted jointly with model formulation, and the anomaly detection strategy. Section IV reports experimental results, including input-data characterization, predictor relevance using a correlation heatmap, predictive performance of ARX, NARX, and RFR models, and an illustrative fault detection test based on a simulated sensor drift. Section V discusses the comparative performance of the models in terms of accuracy, interpretability, computational demand and suitability for future real-time deployment. Section VI concludes the study and proposes future research directions, particularly the implementation of real-time PLC integration and the development of hybrid physics-guided and machine learning frameworks for enhancing system accuracy and interpretability.

II. SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The STC installation consists of three adjustable mirrors mounted on a dual-axis solar tracking structure. These mirrors continuously redirect incoming solar radiation toward a stationary thermal collector. Two motor-driven actuators automatically adjust the mirrors' orientation based on the sun's azimuth and elevation angles throughout the day, thereby maximizing solar energy interception and increasing overall thermal efficiency [16]. The installation also includes a 150-liter insulated storage tank and a load-side heat exchanger with a controllable cooling demand to emulate domestic hot water consumption under various operating conditions. Fig. 1 presents an overview of the main components of the STC infrastructure located in Granges, Switzerland.

Fig. 1. Key components of the STC installation in Granges, Switzerland.

At the core of this setup, a Beckhoff Programmable Logic Controller (PLC) manages real-time data acquisition, system monitoring, and precise motor control [17]. The PLC interfaces with I/O modules to collect and process data from temperature sensors, flow meters, and solar irradiance. It also governs the dual axis tracking mechanism, ensuring accurate and continuous adjustments to optimize solar concentration. As seen in Fig. 2,

the PLC is connected to HOOC Gateways, enabling secure remote access and communication. Node-RED ensures seamless data transfer to InfluxDB, enhancing processing capabilities while maintaining secure database access. Integrated with InfluxDB, Grafana offers an intuitive web-based interface for data visualization and efficient data management. The Grafana dashboard allows monitoring of real-time graphs such as irradiance (S_I), pump flows ($W_{\text{flow STC}}, W_{\text{flow HE}}$), different temperature profiles such as ambient (T_{amb}), tank (T_{tank}), inlet (T_{in}) and outlet (T_{out}) temperatures, heat exchange profile ($T_{\text{inHE}}, T_{\text{outHE}}$), as well as overall thermal power (P_T). In addition, a Human-Machine Interface (HMI) interface, shown in Fig. 3, provides a user-friendly environment for system supervision, anomaly detection, and performance optimization.

Fig. 2. The IoT-based monitoring and control system architecture for the experimental STC installation.

Fig. 3. The HMI interface for real-time monitoring of the STC installation.

III. METHODOLOGY

The AI-based fault detection methodology provides a systematic, data-driven approach to automatically identify faults in the systems by leveraging machine learning techniques. The methodology consists of the following sequential steps:

A. Data Cleaning and Preparation

A short reference period of historical sensor data, typically one week, is selected to represent normal operating conditions. Raw measurements are processed to remove noise and missing values, ensuring data quality for accurate modeling. The cleaned data are structured to facilitate machine learning analysis, providing a consistent baseline for further processing.

B. Feature Preselection

Correlations between the target sensor and other sensors are examined to identify which signals may serve as predictors. Sensors exhibiting strong statistical relationships with the target are retained, reducing the dimensionality of the input space and focusing on the most informative variables.

C. Exhaustive Search of Predictors

In an exhaustive search approach, all possible non-empty combinations of p candidate predictor sensors ($2^p - 1$ subsets)

are evaluated, guaranteeing identification of the subset that optimizes model performance according to the coefficient of determination (R^2). Unlike stepwise or forward selection methods, this approach explores the full predictor space and selects the subset that best balances predictive accuracy and model parsimony [18]. While exhaustive search offers strong guarantees for selecting the optimal predictors in fault detection, its computational cost grows rapidly with the number of predictors, making it practical only for systems with a small to moderate number of sensors.

D. Model Training

Alongside exhaustive search, ARX, NARX, and RFR models are trained for each target sensor using the selected predictors. The models learn the expected normal values of the target sensor based on the correlations with its predictors.

The ARX model [14], [15], [19] expresses the output $y(t)$ of a dynamic system as a linear combination of past outputs $y(t-i)$, past inputs $u(t-j)$, and a noise term $e(t)$. For multiple exogenous inputs, the ARX model generalizes to include all inputs. The equation can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) + a_1y(t-1) + a_2y(t-2) + \dots + a_{n_a}y(t-n_a) \\ = \sum_{k=1}^m (b_{k,1}u_k(t-1) + b_{k,2}u_k(t-2) + \dots \\ + b_{k,n_b}u_k(t-n_b)) + e(t) \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Where $u_k(t)$ is the k -th exogenous input, $b_{k,j}$ are the corresponding input coefficients, m is the total number of inputs, n_a is the order of the output auto regressive part, n_b is the order of the input regression part.

For the NARX model [14], [15], [20], the formulation is like ARX but allows nonlinear relationships between past outputs and inputs. For multiple exogenous inputs, it can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = F(y(t-1), y(t-2), \dots, y(t-n_a), u_1(t-1), \dots \\ , u_1(t-n_b), \dots, u_m(t-1), \dots, u_m(t-n_b)) + e(t) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

Where F is a nonlinear function represented by a neural network or other nonlinear model, $y(t-i)$ are past outputs, $u_k(t-j)$ are past values of the k -th exogenous input, n_a and n_b are the orders of the output and input regressions, m is the number of inputs, and $e(t)$ is a noise term.

For the RFR model [9], [21] applied to time-series or dynamic systems with multiple exogenous inputs, the model predicts the output $y(t)$ as a nonlinear function of past outputs and past input values, similar to a NARX structure, but using a group of decision trees rather than an explicit parametric equation. For multiple inputs, it can be expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} y(t) = \text{RF}(y(t-1), y(t-2), \dots, y(t-n_a), u_1(t-1), \dots \\ , u_1(t-n_b), \dots, u_m(t-1), \dots, u_m(t-n_b)) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Where RF represents the regression function, $y(t-i)$ are past outputs, $u_k(t-j)$ are past values of the k -th exogenous input, n_a and n_b are the output and input lags, m is the number of inputs and the prediction error is implicitly captured by the ensemble nature of the model.

In RFR model, the regressor vector is formed by stacking the selected lagged input–output variables, thereby casting the time-series prediction problem as a supervised regression task. Each decision tree learns a piecewise approximation of the nonlinear mapping from this regressor space to the output using bootstrap sampling and randomized feature selection, which improves model diversity and reduces variance. The final prediction is obtained by averaging the outputs of all trees in the ensemble, resulting in improved generalization and robustness to noise.

E. Prediction and Fault Detection

The trained model predicts the expected value of each target sensor. The predicted values are compared with the actual sensor measurements, and deviations exceeding predefined thresholds are flagged as anomalies. These anomalies correspond to potential faults, enabling automatic and timely detection of issues such as sensor failures, optical or hydraulic malfunctions, or thermal inefficiencies.

IV. RESULTS

This section presents the experimental results obtained from data preprocessing, predictor selection, model training, and fault detection on the monitored STC installation.

The dataset is collected over six days in September 2025, incorporating both sunny and cloudy weather to capture short-term operating variability within a single late-summer period. The dataset does not include seasonal variability such as winter conditions or extreme temperatures. Therefore, the validation reflects only the September operating range, and multi-season evaluation is required to assess long-term generalization. Raw signals are recorded every 2 minutes and filtered by averaging groups of five samples, a configuration determined through recursive testing to achieve the best compromise between noise reduction and dynamic response preservation. This filtering strategy effectively attenuates measurement disturbances while maintaining the thermal fluctuations essential for accurate modeling. Incomplete or inconsistent records are subsequently removed to ensure overall signal integrity. After preprocessing, the resulting measurements as shown in Fig. 4 exhibit realistic evolution of different temperatures, thermal power and irradiance during the active operating period from sunrise to sunset, providing a reliable basis for system modeling.

Fig. 4. Cleaned and filtered time series of key variables, over six representative operating days in September 2025.

Before training the models, correlations among the measured variables are analyzed to identify sensors that provide meaningful predictive information. Statistical relationships between temperatures (T_{amb} , T_{in} , T_{out} , T_{tank}), irradiance (S_I), flow rate ($W_{flow\ STC}$), heat exchanger variables ($W_{flow\ HE}$, $T_{in\ HE}$, $T_{out\ HE}$) and thermal power (P_T) are quantified to eliminate redundant inputs and retain the most informative signals. The resulting heatmap as shown in Fig. 5 highlights variable dependencies and supports initial dimensionality reduction, providing a physically and statistically consistent set of candidate predictors. It is worth noting that the solar irradiance signal was lagged by 4 minutes. This delay was introduced to represent the thermal inertia of the system in response to changes in solar irradiance.

Fig. 5. Correlation heatmap representing relevance and redundancy among solar-thermal variables used for model training.

Next, an exhaustive search procedure is applied to determine the optimal combination of predictors for each target variable. All possible combinations of candidate input sensors are systematically evaluated to identify the subset that minimizes prediction error. The subset that provides the best performance is retained, resulting in a compact and efficient model structure tailored to each modeling approach. Three data-driven models, ARX, NARX, and RFR are trained to estimate four key system variables: inlet and outlet temperatures, storage tank temperature, and delivered thermal power. The parameters and coefficients calculated for the different models are not presented here due to space limitations.

The predictions are evaluated on an independent test day (September 22, 2025), selected for its mixed cloudy and sunny conditions, as illustrated in Figures 6 to 9. Each figure shows both measured and predicted trajectories, demonstrating that each target variable is optimally modeled using its selected predictor set, with the system dynamics accurately reproduced throughout the test day.

Fig. 6. Predicted vs. measured values for inlet temperature, using ARX, NARX, and RFR models, on September 22, 2025 from 10 AM to 5 PM.

Fig. 7. Predicted vs. measured values outlet temperature, using ARX, NARX, and RFR models, on September 22, 2025 from 10 AM to 5 PM.

Fig. 8. Predicted vs. measured values for tank temperature, using ARX, NARX, and RFR models, on September 22, 2025 from 10 AM to 5 PM.

Fig. 9. Predicted vs. measured values thermal power, using ARX, NARX, and RFR models, on September 22, 2025 from 10 AM to 5 PM.

Table I quantifies model performance for the test day using the coefficient of determination R^2 to provide a concise comparison of predictive accuracy for the ARX, NARX, and RFR models. Additional error-based metrics such as RMSE and MAE have also been computed to ensure a complete evaluation, but are not included in this table to avoid overcrowding.

TABLE I. MODEL PERFORMANCE COMPARISON USING COEFFICIENT OF DETERMINATION R^2

	ARX	NARX	RFR
T_{in}	0.975	0.950	0.904
T_{out}	0.975	0.893	0.967
T_{tank}	0.952	0.984	0.989
P_T	0.946	0.957	0.921

Using the trained models, the expected sensor behavior can be estimated and continuously compared with real measurements for anomaly detection. The residual signal, defined as the difference between measured and predicted values, is continuously monitored for anomaly detection. To

establish a reproducible fault detection criterion, the threshold is computed dynamically based on recent system behavior. Specifically, the mean value of the residuals over a sliding time window corresponding to the most recent measurements (e.g., the last 3–4 hours) is calculated and used as the reference level. The fault threshold is then defined relative to this average residual value, reflecting the typical short-term variability of the system under normal operating conditions. Deviations exceeding this calculated threshold are flagged as potential faults.

To demonstrate this capability, an artificial fault was introduced by simulating a PT100 sensor disconnection, causing the inlet temperature T_{in} to drop to ambient conditions. Figure 10 shows a clear deviation between the faulty measurement and the ARX model prediction, sufficient to trigger an anomaly flag. Although based on simulated data, this result highlights the effectiveness of the data-driven model for fault detection.

Fig. 10. Detection of a simulated inlet temperature sensor fault using residual-based monitoring.

V. DISCUSSION

The comparative evaluation of ARX, NARX, and RFR models shows that predictive performance is strongly dependent on the dynamic and physical characteristics of the variables, rather than on a single universally optimal modeling approach. This observation is particularly relevant for fault detection in solar thermal concentrators, where different subsystems exhibit distinct thermal behaviors.

The ARX model provides the best performance for the inlet and outlet fluid temperatures, T_{in} and T_{out} , which are characterized by rapid variations and low thermal inertia. These variables respond quickly to changes in operating conditions and exhibit predominantly linear dynamics with short memory effects. As a result, the linear ARX structure is sufficient to accurately capture their behavior, yielding high predictive accuracy while offering transparency, low computational cost, and straightforward implementation for real-time PLC-based fault detection.

In contrast, the thermal storage tank temperature, T_{tank} , is dominated by strong thermal inertia and slow dynamics, with cumulative energy effects over long time horizons. The RFR model is better suited to this behavior, as its ensemble-based structure can capture long-term dependencies, weak nonlinearities, and complex feature interactions. This explains its superior performance for T_{tank} , despite higher computational requirements.

The NARX model achieves very high accuracy for the thermal power output, P_T , which is governed by a nonlinear interaction between mass flow rate $W_{\text{flow STC}}$ and the temperature difference across the solar thermal concentrator ($T_{\text{out}} - T_{\text{in}}$). This multiplicative dependency cannot be fully captured by linear models, particularly under transient operating conditions. By incorporating nonlinear mappings and temporal dependencies, NARX more effectively represents these coupled effects, leading to improved prediction accuracy and enhanced sensitivity to complex fault signatures.

VI. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE WORK

This study demonstrates the effectiveness of data-driven modeling for fault detection in a solar thermal concentrator system through experimental validation. By combining systematic predictor selection with a comparative evaluation of ARX, NARX, and RFR models, the proposed framework accurately reconstructs system dynamics and enables reliable detection of abnormal deviations. All models exhibit strong predictive performance within the operating range studied. NARX achieves the highest accuracy by capturing nonlinear dynamic interactions, particularly under transient conditions, while RFR shows robustness to complex variable interactions. ARX remains a lightweight and transparent solution well suited for real-time industrial implementation. The limited performance gap between linear and nonlinear models indicates predominantly quasi-linear system behavior under normal conditions. The simulated fault scenario validates the effectiveness of residual-based monitoring for detecting sensor faults and operational anomalies, providing a solid basis for predictive maintenance in solar thermal systems.

However, the validation is based on six days of data collected in September 2025, with testing performed on one independent day. Since solar thermal systems are influenced by seasonal variations in irradiance, ambient temperature, and operating regimes, the results demonstrate proof-of-concept validity within the evaluated operating envelope rather than full annual robustness. Future work will extend the dataset across multiple seasons to assess long-term generalization and will investigate real-time PLC deployment together with hybrid physics-guided machine learning models to further enhance robustness and interpretability.

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